

Speculation on Quantization and Translational Invariance

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In previous notes (1), we argued that the quantum mechanical wavelength $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the translationally invariant classical $P(x)dx=1/L$ ($L=length$) through $P(x)=Pd(px)Pd(-px) = 1/L$. In other words, we argue that translational invariance is a key idea behind the nature of $\exp(ipx)$.

In practical problems, however, one seems to use continuity of $\exp(ipx)$, or a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s and its first derivative d/dx , as well as large x boundary conditions. Practical problems include one dimensional reflection-refraction and bound state problems. As a result, mathematical continuity and boundary conditions lead to physical discrete eigenvalues, such as energy. We suggest that it would be better to have a physical principle behind continuity and discrete eigenvalues and suggest that this principle is translational invariance. We try to examine this in two ways.

First, in the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction, continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and the first derivative at $x=0$ solve the problem. We ask, however: What happens away from the $x=0$ point in terms of translational invariance? We show that at all points an integer number of wavelengths from $x=0$, one has the same slope and magnitude of the function value. Here $C\exp(ip2x)$ is the refracted function and $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$, the incident plus reflected. Thus, translational invariance in space is established and is equivalent in this problem to continuity of the functions and first derivatives at $x=0$.

In the case of a bound state problem, one no longer has a single $\exp(ipx)$ or even two ($\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$). Rather, one has a linear combination. We argue, however, that a linear combination is composed of $\exp(ipx)$ s which each demonstrate translational invariance and are continuous. We suggest that it is the underlying physical $\exp(ipx)$ s and their feature of translational invariance which leads one to make $W=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ continuous, with its first derivative at boundaries such as in a square well potential. We suggest that the crest-trough feature of bound states (e.g. oscillator) is ultimately due to the translational invariant nature of $\exp(ipx)$ and that this crest-trough behaviour lead to orthogonal W_n states just as $\exp(ipx)$ s are orthogonal. The $W_n=0$ condition at $x=\pm\infty$ simply leads to a crest, followed by a crest-trough, followed by a crest-trough-crest appearing in the bound region. We suggest that this is still reminiscent of the translationally invariant crest-troughs of $\exp(ipx)$

Thus, ultimately we suggest that discrete quantum values are linked to translational invariance of $\exp(ipx)$ which we think should be the case because we argue that the very form of $\exp(ipx)$ is due to translational invariance, i.e. to $P(x) \text{ classical} = Pd(px)Pd(-px)=1/L$, where $Pd(px)=\exp(ipx)$.

Free Particle Wavefunction and Translational Invariance

We have argued in (1) that the classical translationally invariant $P(x)dx= 1/L dx$ (where L is length) must consist of p and $-p$ (momentum) at each x point. We thus suggested that:

$$P(x) = Pd(px) P(-px) = 1/L \text{ or } Pd(px) = \exp(ipx) / \text{sqrt}(L) \quad ((1))$$

For a discussion of the form $\exp(ipx)$ as the argument of P_d , a dynamical directional probability, see (1). One may see that $\exp(ipx)$ has equally spaced wavelengths \hbar/p which represent a kind of nonlocal behaviour creating translational invariance approximately through periodicity. Within each wavelength is a crest and trough such that one average one has action-reaction or an average constant. Thus, there is a discreteness (wavelength) linked with translational invariance if one has a single p (momentum) value.

In other words, we suggest that translational invariance is key to the form $\exp(ipx)$. This begs the question: If translational invariance is key, why is it that in practical problems one matches $\exp(ipx)$ or linear combinations and the first derivative d/dx at a junction and then imposes large x boundary conditions. This approach is used both in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem and in bound state problems which lead to discrete energy levels. Continuity (function and first derivative) at a junction and large x boundary conditions are mathematical conditions, which though true, should be linked to a physical condition, we argue. Furthermore, if translational invariance is key to $\exp(ipx)$, then this physical condition should be linked to translational invariance, we argue.

Free Particle Orthogonality

We first note that in the above discussion p and $-p$ may be any value. For $P(x)=1/L$ one could have mixed p_1, p_2, p_3 and $-p_1, -p_2, -p_3$ etc. In that situation, what does $\exp(ipx)$ suggest? We consider:

$$W = \sum_j a_j \exp(ip_j x) \quad \text{and} \quad W^*W = \sum_{j,k} a_j a_k \exp(-ip_j x) \exp(ip_k x) \quad ((2))$$

If one integrates ((2)) x , cross terms should vanish because translational invariance applies to each $p, -p$ pair. There is interference locally, but globally, integration removes it and one has orthogonality. This, $\exp(ipx)$ does not simply represent translational invariance, but also orthogonality for different p values. It is fine to have local interference because the crest-trough wavelength region is finite and only represents translational invariance on average.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

One dimensional photon reflection-refraction can be solved by considering $\exp(ipx)$ with $E=pc$ for two media, one with index of refraction n_1 and the other with n_2 . By imposing continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and the first derivative at $x=0$, one may solve the problem (2) i.e.

$$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at} \quad x=0 \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x) - B p_1 \exp(-ip_1 x) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \quad \text{at} \quad x=0 \quad ((3b))$$

One may solve for B/A and C/A (see (2)) and then note that:

$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \rightarrow AA p_1 = BB p_1 + CC p_2$ where AA is incident flux, BB, reflected, and CC refracted and AA/c1 is probability. ((4))

It seems that the continuity of the $\exp(ipx)$ functions at $x=0$ (together with continuity of d/dx at $x=0$) is the key idea. If $\exp(ipx)$ follows from translational invariance, is continuity (function and derivative) a second, independent, key idea?

We suggest that translational invariance is still very much the key idea and that continuity of function and first derivative d/dx is consistent with translational invariance.

To see this, one may note that for $x \neq 0$:

$A \exp(ip_1 x) + B \exp(-ip_1 x)$ versus $C \exp(ip_2 x)$ ((5a))

$A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x) - B p_1 \exp(-ip_1 x)$ versus $C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x)$ ((5b))

Thus, the matching at $x=0$ holds for other x points if $p_1 x_1 = p_2 x_2 = 2\pi \cdot 3.14 \cdot n$, where n is an integer and so there is translational invariance at least periodically.

If one did not have a reflected ray, then $A \exp(ip_1 x)$ versus $C \exp(ip_2 x)$ and $A p_1 \exp(ip_1 x)$ and $C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x)$ would be incompatible as noted in (1).

Thus, continuity at $x=0$ is related to translational invariance in the sense of periodicity for other x values.. We suggest that the continuity condition is a consequence of desiring this periodicity.

Bound States

Bound states are considered to be created by:

$W_n = \sum_p a_n(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((6))

Given that $\exp(ipx)$ s are used and that the form, $\exp(ipx)$, is based on translational invariance, we suggest that this translational invariance of $\exp(ipx)$ should not disappear. In fact, we suggest that the continuity of each $\exp(ipx)$ and its derivative in all of x implies that continuity be imposed at special junctions, just as in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem discussed above.

In particular, if one has an infinite potential well with the condition that $W_n=0$ for $x < 0$ and $x > L$, we note that $\exp(ipx)$ s still exist in that region and so there should be continuity of W_n at $x=0$ and $x=L$. This suggests that $W_n(x=0)=W_n(x=L)=0$ which leads to discrete energy values. We suggest, however, that the underlying idea here is that of translational invariance of the $\exp(ipx)$ s which implies continuity of the function and its first derivative. (Note: A Fourier series of a step function which leads to a continuous function.)

For the case of a square well which is not infinite, the same continuity of W_n and its first derivative occurs. One must also have $W_n \rightarrow 0$ at $x = \pm \infty$. These conditions, however, are not independent of the continuity of the translationally invariant (to an extent through periodicity) $\exp(ipx)$ s. We suggest that a partial crest may be created inside the well which is then joined with an $\exp(-k_1 x)$ outside creating a "kind of" crest which is the best one may have at the junction.

For the case of an harmonic oscillator there are no special junctions, but only $W_n=0$ at $x=\pm \infty$. We note, however, that the crests and troughs (unequal in height and width) seem to be linked to the periodicity of the $\exp(ipx)$ s. As we have argued before, this periodicity like that of $\exp(ipx)$ leads to orthogonal wavefunctions, but the additional $W_n=0$ at $x=\pm \infty$ seems to force discrete energy levels. It is the combination of the $W_n=0$ at $x=\pm \infty$ and the crest trough picture (ultimately linked to the periodicity of $\exp(ipx)$ s) which yields the discrete energy levels and not the $W_n=0$ at $x=\pm \infty$ alone, we argue.

One may note that in the case of $\exp(ipx)$, one has translational invariance in all x and so one can have crests and troughs in all x . This leads to an infinite number of crests and troughs. If, however, one has localisation as in the case of a potential, one may start with one crest, followed by a crest-trough combination etc. Thus, keeping the crest-trough form, which already appears in $\exp(ipx)$ and is countable, one starts from 1 and increases in integer values which leads to discrete energy levels. In short, we suggest that the idea of crests and troughs, which seems to be central in bound problems is ultimately linked to the equal crest trough of $\exp(ipx)$ which follows from spatial invariance, i.e. $P(x)=P_d(px)P_d(-px) = 1/L$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one considers $\exp(ipx)$, a free particle wavefunction, to be based on the translational invariance of $P(x) = 1/L$, where $P(x)$ is classical and equal to $P_d(px)P_d(-px)$ where $P_d(px)=\exp(ipx)$, then this idea of translational invariance should appear in practical problems. It seems, however, that there exist two other principles namely continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ or a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s and continuity of the first derivative at a special junction, if one exists and, secondly, the vanishing of W_n , the bound state linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s at $x=\pm \infty$.

We argue for the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction that continuity is linked to translational invariance (at least periodically) and suggest this is also the case for the square well infinite or non-infinite potential. In the case of a non-infinite potential, $W_n=0$ at $x=\pm \infty$ is really linked to crest-troughs appearing in a localized "bound" region. These crest-troughs are linked to the crest-troughs of the underlying $\exp(ipx)$ s and so one creates energy levels by introducing a crest in the bound region, followed by a crest-trough etc. In the case of a non-infinite square-well potential, the crest-troughs exist in the well, but for an oscillator, the crest-trough region grows in length.

We suggest that this behaviour and the orthogonality of W_n s follows from the behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$ s which in turn follows from the notion of translational invariance which gives rise to nonlocal regions of the size of a wavelength which contain an equally sized crest and trough which on average give the semblance of translational invariance within the wavelength region.

References

- 1 Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Conservation of Momentum and Spatial Invariance (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
- 2 [.https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change)